

A CHARACTERIZATION OF NEUTROSOPHIC σ BAIRE SPACE ON FUZZY SETTING

E.Poongothai¹, E. Kalaivani²

¹Department of mathematics, Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College, (Co-Ed), Tiruvannamalai-606603, Tamil Nadu, India ; epoongothai5@gmail.com

²Department of mathematics, Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College, (Co-Ed), Tiruvannamalai-606603, Tamil Nadu, India; kalai12feb@gmail.com

*Correspondence: epoongothai5@gmail.com; Tel.: (optional; include country code)

Abstract. In this paper we investigate several characterization of F. neu. σ -baire spaces and study conditions under which a fy. neu. top. space we becomes a F. neu. σ -B.S. and also discussed F. neu. almost resolvable space, F. neu. hyperconnected space, F. neu. submaximal space.

Keywords: F. neu. F_σ -set, F. neu. G_δ -set, F. neu. σ -first and second category set, F. neu. nowhere dense set, fuzzy dense set, F. neu. σ -nwd set, F. neu. σ -first category space, F. neu. σ - second category space, F. neu. σ -B.S, F. neu. almost resolvable space , F. neu. hyperconnected , F. neu. submaximal space.)

1. Introduction

The fuzzy idea was invaded all branches of science as far back as the presentation of fuzzy sets by L. A. Zadeh [10]. The important concept of fuzzy topological space was offered by C.L. Chang [2]. The idea of fuzzy σ - Baire Spaces was introduced by G. Thangaraj and E. Poongothai [8]. The concept of neutrosophic sets was defined with membership, non-membership and indeterminacy degrees. In 2017, Veereswari [9] introduced Fy. neutrosophic topological spaces. The idea of fy. neutrosophic Baire spaces was introduced by E. Poongothai and E. Padmavathi [3].

In this paper, we discussed and established several characterization of neutrosophic σ -baire space on fuzzy setting. Also, we introduce to study the conditions under witch a neu. top. space becomes a neu. σ -B.S on fuzzy setting.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [1] A fy. neutrosophic set A on the universe of discourse X is defined as $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $x \in X$ where $T, I, F : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x), F_A(x) \leq 3$. With the condition $0 \leq T_{A^*}(x) + I_{A^*}(x), F_{A^*}(x) \leq 2$

Definition 2.2. [1] A fy. neutrosophic set A is a subset of a fy. neutrosophic set B (i.e.,) $A \subseteq B$ for all x if $T_A(x) \leq T_B(x)$, $I_A(x) \leq I_B(x)$, $F_A(x) \geq F_B(x)$

Definition 2.3. [1] Let X be a non-empty set, and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$, $B = \langle x, T_B(x), I_B(x), F_B(x) \rangle$ be two fy. neutrosophic sets. Then

$$A \cup B = \langle x, \max(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \max(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \min(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$$

$$A \cap B = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), T_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), F_B(x)) \rangle$$

Definition 2.4. [1] The difference between two fy. neutrosophic sets A and B is defined as $A \setminus B(x) = \langle x, \min(T_A(x), F_B(x)), \min(I_A(x), 1 - I_B(x)), \max(F_A(x), T_B(x)) \rangle$

Definition 2.5. [1] A fy. neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be null or empty fy. neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 0$, $I_A(x) = 0$, $F_A(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 0_N

Definition 2.6. [1] A fy. neutrosophic set A over the universe X is said to be absolute (universe) fy. neutrosophic set if $T_A(x) = 1$, $I_A(x) = 1$, $F_A(x) = 0$ for all $x \in X$. It is denoted by 1_N

Definition 2.7. [1] The complement of a fy. neutrosophic set A is denoted by A^C and is defined as $A^C = \langle x, T_{A^C}(x), I_{A^C}(x), F_{A^C}(x) \rangle$ where $T_{A^C}(x) = F_A(x)$, $I_{A^C}(x) = 1 - I_A(x)$, $F_{A^C}(x) = T_A(x)$. The complement of fy. neutrosophic set A can also be defined as $A^C = 1_N - A$.

Definition 2.8. [1] A fy. neutrosophic topology on a non-empty set X is a τ of fy. neutrosophic sets in X satisfying the following axioms.

- (i) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
- (ii) $A_1 \cap A_2 \in \tau$ for any $A_1, A_2 \in \tau$
- (iii) $\cup A_i \in \tau$ for any arbitrary family $\{A_i : i \in J\} \in \tau$

In this case the pair (X, τ) is called fy. neutrosophic top. space and any fy. neutrosophic set in τ is known as fy. neutrosophic open set in X

Definition 2.9. [1] The complement A^C of a fy. neutrosophic set A in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (X, τ) is called fy. neutrosophic closed set in X .

Definition 2.10. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space and $A = \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle$ be a fy. neutrosophic set in X . Then the closure and Interior of A are defined by

$$I.(A) = \cup\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$$

$$C.(A) = \cap\{G : G \text{ is a fuzzy neutrosophic closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq G\}$$

Definition 2.11. [1] Let (X, τ) be a fy. neutrosophic topological space over X . Then (i) $C.(A^C) = (I. A)^C$, (ii) $I.(A^C) = (cl A)^C$

Definition 2.12. [5] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic F_σ -set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $\overline{A_{N_i}} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.13. [5] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic G_δ -set in (P, τ_N) if $A_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where $A_{N_i} \in \tau_N$ for $i \in I$

Definition 2.14. [5] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic dense if there exist no $fnCS B_N$ in (P, τ_N) s.t $A_N \subset B_N \subset 1_X$. That is $fn(A_N)^- = 1_N$

Definition 2.15. [3] A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in a fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called a fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense set if there exist no non zero $fnOS B_N$ in (P, τ_N) s.t $B_N \subset fn(A_N)^-$. That is $fn(((A_N)^-)^+) = 0_N$

Definition 2.16. [3] Let (P, τ_N) be a fy. neutrosophic top. space. A fy. neutrosophic set A_N in (P, τ_N) is called fy. neutrosophic one category set if $A_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Any other fy. neutrosophic set in (P, τ_N) is said to be of fy. neutrosophic two category.

Definition 2.17. [3] A fy. neutrosophic top. space (P, τ_N) is called fy. neutrosophic one category space if the fy. neutrosophic set 1_X is a fy. neutrosophic one category set in (P, τ_N) . That is $1_X = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} A_{N_i}$, where A_{N_i} 's are fy. neutrosophic nowh. dense sets in (P, τ_N) . Otherwise (P, τ_N) will be called a fy. neutrosophic two category space.

3. A Characterization of Fuzzy Neutrosophic σ Baire Space on Fuzzy Setting

Definition 3.1. Let (X_N, T_N) be a Fy. neutrosophic topological space then (X_N, T_N) is called a F. neutrosophic σ -Baire space if $I.(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0$, where λ_{N_i} 's are F. neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 3.2. [5] Let (X_N, T_N) be a Fy. neutrosophic topological space. Then the following are equivalent

- (1) (X_N, T_N) is a F. neutrosophic σ -Baire space.

- (2) $I.(\lambda_N) = 0$ for every F . neutrosophic σ - first category set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) .
 (3) $C.(\mu_N) = 1$ for every F . neutrosophic σ -residual set μ_N in (X_N, T_N)

Theorem 3.3. [5] In a Fy . neutrosophic topological space (X_N, T_N) a fy . neutrosophic set λ_N is F . neutrosophic σ -nowhere dense in (X_N, T_N) if and only if $1 - \lambda_N$ F . neutrosophic dense and F . neutrosophic G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) .

Theorem 3.4. [3] If λ_N is a F . neu. dense and F . neu. G_δ -set in a fy . neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) then $1 - \lambda_N$ is a F . neu. first category set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 3.5. If the fuzzy neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F . neu. σ -Baire space, then $C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 1$, where the fuzzy sets (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F . neu. dense set and F . neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) .

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) be a F . neu. dense set. and F . neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) By theorem 3.3 $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are fuzzy neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then the fuzzy neu. set $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$ is a F . neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Now $I.(\lambda_N) = I.(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})) = I.(1 - [\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})]) = 1 - C.(1 - [\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})])$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a F . neu. σ -baire space, by theorem 3.1, we have $I.(\lambda_N) = 0$. Then $1 - C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. This implies that $C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 1$ \square

Proposition 3.6. If the fy . neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F . neu. σ -B.S, then $I.[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$, where the F . neu. sets $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s ($i = 1$ to ∞) are fuzzy first category sets formed from the fuzzy neu. dense and F . neu. G_δ -set λ_{N_i} in (X_N, T_N) .

Proof. Let the fy . neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F . neu. σ -B.S and the F . neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) be F . neu. dense and F . neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . By prop. 3.5, $C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 1$. Then $1 - C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. This implies that $I.[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. Also by theorem 3.4, $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are F . neu. first category sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence $I.[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$, where the fuzzy neu. sets $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s ($i = 1$ to ∞) are fuzzy neu. first category sets formed from the F . neu. dense and F . neu. G_δ -set λ_{N_i} in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Theorem 3.7. [3] Let (X_N, T_N) be a fy . neu. top. space. Then the following are equivalent.

- (1) (X_N, T_N) is a F . neu. B.S.
 (2) $f_n(A_N)^+ = 0_N$ for every F . neu. first category set A_N in (X_N, T_N) .
 (3) $f_n(A_N)^- = 1$, for every F . neu. residual set B_N in (X_N, T_N) .

Proposition 3.8. If the F . neu. first category sets are formed from the F . neu. dense and F . neu. G_δ -sets in a F . neu. σ -B.S (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) . is a F . neu. B.S.

Proof. Let the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) be a fuzzy neu. σ -B.S. By prop.3.6, $I.[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$, where the F. neu. sets $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. first category sets formed from the F. neu. dense and and F. neu. G_δ -sets λ_{N_i} in (X_N, T_N) . Now $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}[I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] \leq [I.(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i}))]$. Then we have $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}[I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. This implies that $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$, where $1 - \lambda_{N_i}$ is a fuzzy neu. first category set in (X_N, T_N) . By theorem 3.7, (X_N, T_N) is a fu.neu. B.S. \square

Theorem 3.9. [5] *A fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is called F. neu. σ -first category if the F. neu. set 1_{X_N} is a F. neu. σ - first category space in (X_N, T_N) . That is $1_{X_N} = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$ Where λ_{N_i} 's are F. neu. σ - nowhere dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Otherwise (X_N, T_N) will be called a F. neu. σ - second category space.*

Proposition 3.10. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -first category space, then (X_N, T_N) is not a F. neu. σ -Baire space.*

Proof. Let the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -first category space. Then $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1_{X_N}$, where λ_{N_i} 's are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $I.\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) = I.(1_{X_N}) = 1 \neq 0$. Hence, (X_N, T_N) is not a F. neu. σ -B.S. \square

Proposition 3.11. *If $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -set in a fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -second category space.*

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . By theorem 3.3, $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$ implies that $1 - \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1$. Then $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1$. Hence (X_N, T_N) is not a F. neu. σ -first category space and therefore (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -second category space. \square

Proposition 3.12. *If λ_N is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , then there is a F. neu. F_σ -set δ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$*

Proof. Let λ_N is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i})$ where (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $[1 - C.(\lambda_{N_i})]$'s are F. neu. open sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\mu_N = \bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}[1 - C.(\lambda_{N_i})]$ is a F. neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) and $1 - \mu_N = 1 - [\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty}(1 - C.(\lambda_{N_i}))] = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(C.(\lambda_{N_i}))$. Now $\lambda = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(\lambda_{N_i}) \leq \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty}(C.(\lambda_{N_i})) = 1 - \mu_N$. That is, $\lambda_N \leq 1 - \mu_N$ and $1 - \mu_N$ is a F. neu. F_σ -set in (X_N, T_N) . Let $\delta_N = 1 - \mu_N$. Hence, if λ_N is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , then there is a F. neu. F_σ -set δ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $\lambda_N \leq \delta_N$. \square

Proposition 3.13. *If σ_N is a F. neu. σ -residual set in a fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) such that $\eta_N \leq \delta_N$ where η_N is a F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S.*

Proof. Let σ_N be a F. neu. σ -residual set in a fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) . Then $1 - \delta_N$ is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Now by prop.3.12, there is a F. neu. F_σ -set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $1 - \delta_N \leq \mu_N$. This implies that $1 - \mu_N \leq \sigma_N$. Let $\eta_N = 1 - \mu_N$. Then η_N is a F. neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) and $\eta_N \leq \delta_N$ implies that $C(\eta_N) \leq C(\delta_N)$. If $C(\eta_N) = 1$, then we have $C(\delta_N) = 1$. Hence, by theorem3.2, (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S. \square

Proposition 3.14. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ B.S and if $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) = 1$, then there exists atleast one F. neu. F_σ -set λ_{N_i} such that $I(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$*

Proof. Suppose that $I(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$, for $i = 1$ to ∞ , where (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) = 1$. implies that $I[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})] = I[1] = 1 \neq 0$, a contradiction to (X_N, T_N) being a F. neu. σ -B.S. Hence $I(\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$, for atleast one F. neu. F_σ -set λ_{N_i} in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.15. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is F. neu. σ -B.S, then no non-zero F. neu. open set is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proof. Let λ_N be a non zero F. neu. open set in a F. neu. σ -B.S (X_N, T_N) . Suppose that $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$, where the fuzzy neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . then $I(\lambda_{N_i}) = I(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}))$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S, $I(\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 0$. This implies that $I(\lambda_N) = 0$. Then we will have $\lambda_N = 0$, which is a contradiction. Since $\lambda_N \in T_N$ implies that $I(\lambda_N) = \lambda_N \neq 0$. Hence no non-zero F. neu. open set is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Theorem 3.16. [4] *A fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is called a F. neu. submaximal space if for each F. neu. set λ_N in (X_N, T_N) such that $C(\lambda_N) = 1$ then $C(\lambda_N \in T_N)$ in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proposition 3.17. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. submaximal space and if λ_N is a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , then λ_N is a F. neu. first category set in (X_N, T_N)*

Proof. Let $\lambda_N = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ be a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) , where the fuzzy sets (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. σ -nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then we have $I(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$ and (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. F_σ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $I(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$, implies that $1 - I(\lambda_N) = 1 - 0 = 1$ and hence $C(1 - \lambda_N) = 1$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. submaximal

space, the F. neu. dense sets $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are F. neu. open sets in (X_N, T_N) and hence λ_{N_i} 's are F. neu. closed sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = \lambda_{N_i}$ and $I.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$ implies that $I.C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = I.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. That is (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. nwd sets (X_N, T_N) . Therefore $\lambda = \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})$ is a F. neu. first category set in (X_N, T_N) . \square

Proposition 3.18. *If the F. neu. top space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S and F. neu. submaximal space, then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. B.S.*

Proof. Let μ_N be a F. neu. σ -first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. submaximal space, by prop3.17, μ_N is a F. neu.first category set in (X_N, T_N) . Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S, by them3.2 $I.(\mu_N) = 0$. Hence, for the F. neu. first category set μ_N in (X_N, T_N) , we have $I.(\mu_N) = 0$. Therefore, by thm.3.7, (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. B.S. \square

Theorem 3.19. [4] *A fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is called a F. neu.P-space if countable intersection of F. neu. open sets in (X_N, T_N) is F. neu. open. That is, every non-zero F. neu. G_δ -set in (X_N, T_N) is F. neu. open in (X_N, T_N) .*

Proposition 3.20. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S and F. neu. P-space, then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. B.S.*

Proof. Let the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) be a F. neu. σ -B.S. Then, by prop.3.5, $C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})] = 1$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now from, $C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})] = 1$, we have $1 - C.[\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. This implies that $I.[\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda_{N_i})] = 0$. Since the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. dense in (X_N, T_N) , $C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1$. Then we have $1 - C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. This implies that $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. This implies that $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. Also, since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. P-space, the non-zero F. neu. G_δ -sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) , are F. neu. open in (X_N, T_N) . Then $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are F. neu. closed sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then $C.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 1 - \lambda_{N_i}$ and $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$ implies that $I.C.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. That is $(1 - \lambda_{N_i})$'s are F. neu. nwd sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence, by thm.3.7, (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. B.S. \square

Theorem 3.21. [4] *A F. neu. top space (X_N, T_N) is called a F. neu. almost resolvable space if $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) are such that $I.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. Otherwise (X_N, T_N) is called a fuzzy neu. almost irresolvable space.*

Proposition 3.22. *If the fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. almost resolvable space, then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -second category space.*

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) be the F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Now $C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 1$ implies that $1 - C.(\lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. That is, $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. almost irresolvable space, $\bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) are such that $I.(1 - \lambda_{N_i}) = 0$. Now $I. \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda_{N_i}) \neq 1$ implies that $1 - \bigvee_{i=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$. Hence we have $\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i}) \neq 0$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -sets in a fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) . Thus, by prop.3.11 (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -second category space. \square

Theorem 3.23. [4] A fy. neu. top. space (X_N, T_N) is called a F. neu. hyperconnected space if every F. neu. open set λ_N is F. neu. dense in (X_N, T_N) . That is, $C.(\lambda_N) = 1$ for all $0 \neq \lambda_N \in T_N$

Theorem 3.24. If $C.(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 1$, where λ_{N_i} 's are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_σ -sets in (X_N, T_N) . Then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S.

Proposition 3.25. If $C.(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 1$, where the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's are F. neu. G_δ -sets in a F. neu. hyperconnected and F. neu. P -space (X_N, T_N) , then (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S.

Proof. Let (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) be the F. neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) such that $C.(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 1$. Since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. P -space, the F. neu. G_δ -sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) , are F. neu. open in (X_N, T_N) . Also since (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. hyperconnected space, the F. neu. open sets (λ_{N_i}) 's in (X_N, T_N) , are F. neu. dense sets in (X_N, T_N) . Hence the F. neu. sets (λ_{N_i}) 's ($i = 1$ to ∞) are F. neu. dense and F. neu. G_δ -sets in (X_N, T_N) and $C.(\bigwedge_{i=1}^{\infty} (\lambda_{N_i})) = 1$. Hence by thm3.24 (X_N, T_N) is a F. neu. σ -B.S. \square

4. Conclusion

In this paper several characterization of F. neutrosophic σ -Baire space and other F. neutrosophic spaces are discussed and established.

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